

Lung cancer dataset used for the classification phase of the Open Challenge

ID: a96b56cd-59d4-444a-8e59-32a7fb0d7dea

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/a96b56cd-59d4-444a-8e59-32a7fb0d7dea/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 1239

Subjects count: 482

Age range: Between 33 years and 87 years

Sex: Male, Female, Unkown

Body part(s): CHEST, ABDOMEN, NECK, BRAIN, SPINE, LUNG, HEAD, WHOLEBODY, THORAX, THORAX INJECTE, EXTREMITY, THORAX / ABDOMEN, UNKNOWN, TOTAL BODY, LSPINE, CSPINE, TORAX, TDM THORAX / ABD, TB COLLO, TC TOTAL BODY, Unknown

Modality: CT, PT, DX